

PESU – Advanced Project on Mechatronics

Roman Krajka

*Department of Energy and
Mechanical Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo
roman.krajka@aalto.fi*

Félix Calmont

*Department of Energy and
Mechanical Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo
felix.calmont@aalto.fi*

Abstract

This report presents the redesign, assembly, instrumentation and preliminary validation of an upgraded Pneumatic Energy Saving Unit test bench. The project builds on the previous work carried out by Lorenzo Ceppari and aims to provide a more modular, mobile and maintainable experimental setup for future research activities. The new system is mounted on an aluminium-profile structure, equipped with pneumatic actuators, pressure sensors, flow meters, temperature sensors and a data acquisition architecture.

The main contribution of the project is the construction of a functional and reconfigurable pneumatic platform. Although complete efficiency testing could not be finalized within the available time, the mechanical and pneumatic integration was completed, the measurement architecture was documented, and the principal sensor connections and scaling equations were established. The Nokeval 641 converter for flow meter Q_1 was connected and configured but still requires experimental validation. In addition, SIKO wire transducers were selected for the displacement measurements required for future energy-balance calculations. Remaining work mainly concerns final signal validation, completion of the displacement measurement setup, and energy-balance analysis.

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1 Introduction

Compressed-air systems are widely used in industrial automation because of their robustness, simplicity and high power density. However, they are also known for relatively poor energy efficiency, especially when exhaust air is simply released to the atmosphere after actuation. The purpose of a Pneumatic Energy Saving Unit is to reduce compressed-air consumption by recovering part of the pneumatic energy contained in the exhaust flow and reusing it within the circuit.

The present project consisted in rebuilding and upgrading an existing PESU-based experimental setup. The previous version, developed in connection with Lorenzo Ceppari's work, demonstrated the operating principle but was less suitable for future experimental use. The new version was therefore designed with three main objectives:

- 1) improve the mechanical layout and mobility of the setup;
- 2) make the pneumatic circuit cleaner, more accessible and easier to modify;
- 3) prepare the system for quantitative measurements of pressure, flow rate, temperature and actuator motion.

The report is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the operating principle of the PESU. Section 3 describes the mechanical support structure. Section 4 presents the pneumatic components and their installation. Section 5 describes the automation and measurement architecture. Section 6 summarizes the final updates performed after the main assembly phase. Section 7 lists the remaining work required for full experimental validation.

2 Operating principle of the PESU

The Pneumatic Energy Saving Unit is based on the principle of exhaust-air recovery. In a conventional pneumatic actuator circuit, compressed air is supplied to one chamber of the cylinder while the opposite chamber exhausts air at a reduced pressure. This exhaust flow still contains recoverable energy. Instead of releasing it directly to the atmosphere, the PESU redirects part of this reduced-pressure air into a recovery circuit.

The system described in the related patent consists of a pressure-increasing unit connected to the main compressed-air source and to the actuator exhaust line. The main functional elements are:

- a connection to the main compressed-air supply;
- a connection to the reduced-pressure exhaust line;
- a pressure intensifier;
- storage tanks;
- a pressure controller;

- substitution means allowing recovered air to be redirected to the actuator circuit when the recovered pressure is sufficient.

During operation, the actuator is supplied through a pressure controller and a directional valve. The exhaust air from the actuator is directed toward the PESU. The remaining pneumatic energy is partly used by the pressure intensifier to produce higher-pressure air. When the PESU circuit pressure exceeds the pressure available from the main supply line at the relevant connection point, recovered air can substitute part of the compressed air that would otherwise be drawn from the main source. The expected benefit is a reduction in compressed-air consumption and, consequently, a reduction in the energy required for air compression and treatment.

Figure 1: General operating principle of the PESU.

3 Mechanical support structure

3.1 Design requirements

In the original setup, the components were mounted on a fixed wooden board. Although this solution was sufficient for initial testing, it was not optimal for future laboratory use. The upgraded test bench had to be mobile, modular and easy to reconfigure. For this reason, the new support structure was designed as an aluminium-profile cart mounted on wheels.

The selected structure uses 45 mm aluminium profiles and M8 spring-loaded square nuts. This solution allows components to be added, removed or repositioned without dismantling the whole frame. The pneumatic components are attached to the vertical frame, whereas the PESU and the 60 L air tank are placed on the horizontal aluminium base plate. Two pneumatic actuators are mounted on opposite short sides of the cart to reproduce a representative actuator load.

3.2 Preliminary dimensions and modelling

The global dimensions of the structure were defined from the dimensions of the major components. The main measurements used during the design phase are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Main dimensions used for the preliminary design of the support structure.

Element	Approximate dimensions
PESU	$l = 460 \text{ mm}$, $w = 250 \text{ mm}$, $h = 650 \text{ mm}$
Air tank	$d = 300 \text{ mm}$, $h = 1050 \text{ mm}$
Pneumatic actuator	total length = 850 mm, stroke = 700 mm
Aluminium profile	45 mm \times 45 mm section
Base plate	1000 mm \times 500 mm

A simplified 3D model was prepared in *Blender 4.4.0*. The model was not intended as a detailed CAD representation, but as a global layout tool to verify the relative positions of the PESU, air tank, actuators, wheels, base plate and aluminium profiles.

Figure 2: Preliminary 3D model of the mobile PESU test bench.

Figure 3: Assembled aluminium-profile structure with the two actuators.

3.3 Manufacturing of the structure

The aluminium profiles and the aluminium base plate were manufactured using the Design Factory facilities. The main workshop tools were a cold circular saw, a lever shear, a pillar drilling machine and a folding machine. The aluminium profiles were cut to the lengths listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Aluminium components used for the frame.

Quantity	Length	Purpose
4	1710 mm	Main vertical profiles
4	955 mm	Long horizontal profiles
4	455 mm	Short horizontal profiles
2	910 mm	Intermediate profiles with access hole for square nuts
2	410 mm	Intermediate profiles with access hole for square nuts
1	1000 mm × 500 mm	Aluminium base plate

Access holes were drilled near the ends of the intermediate profiles. These holes allow additional M8 square nuts to be inserted later, making it possible to add components without disassembling the frame.

The base plate was cut to 1000 mm by 500 mm. Its relief pattern caused local thickness variations between approximately 1.5 mm and 2.5 mm. Despite this variation, the plate could be cut with the lever shear without difficulty. Holes of 13 mm diameter were then drilled to mount the wheels using bolts and washers.

4 Pneumatic component installation

4.1 Component selection

The initial intention was to reproduce the component selection used in the previous PESU setup. In practice, some components were unavailable or already used in other projects. Since the objective was to build a functional test bench rather than an exact replica, several components were replaced or adapted. The final selection includes shut-off valves, filters, a storage tank, check valves, reed and position sensors, directional valves, speed controllers, mufflers, pressure sensors, temperature sensors, flow meters, two double-acting cylinders and two wire-actuated displacement sensors selected for future position measurements.

Table 3: Main pneumatic and measurement components.

Qty.	Label	Component	Code / manufacturer	Main specification
1	1 _A	Shut-off valve with exhaust port	VHS40-F04A	–
1	1 _B	Shut-off valve with exhaust port	VHS40-F04B	–
1	1 _C	Shut-off valve with exhaust port	VHS40-F04-M-D	–
4	1 _D	Shut-off valve with exhaust port	EVHS3500-F02-X116	–
1	2 _A	Air filter	AW40-F04E-B	Oil filter
1	2 _B	Air filter	AFD40-F04-A	Vapour filter
1	2 _C	Air filter	AW40K-F04-B	Oil filter
1	2 _D	Air filter	AFM40-F04D-A	Oil filter
1	2 _E	Air filter	AFM40-F04-A	Oil filter
1	3	Check valve	AK2000	Removed after first tests
1	4	Air tank	VB3306/276	Volume: 60 L
2	5 _A	Reed sensor	D-A93	Cylinder end-position detection
2	5 _B	Position sensor	D-M9PW	Cylinder end-position detection
2	6	5/3 directional valve	SY9320-5YZ-03F-Q	Actuator control
2	7	Speed controller	AS3002F	Flow adjustment
2	8 _A	Muffler	AN30-03	Exhaust silencing
2	8 _B	Muffler	AN20-02	Exhaust silencing
3	8 _C	Muffler	AN200	Exhaust silencing
6	P	Pressure sensor	PSE530-M5	Gauge pressure, analog voltage output
3	T	Temperature sensor	Parker IQAN-ST / 20073657	Analog voltage output
1	Q ₁	Flow meter	PF2MC7501-F04-D-M	5 L/min to 500 L/min, 4 mA to 20 mA output
1	Q ₂	Flow meter	PFMC7102-F04-E	10 L/min to 1000 L/min, 1 V to 5 V output
1	Q ₃	Flow meter	PFMC7501-F04-E	5 L/min to 500 L/min, 1 V to 5 V output
2	Actuator	Double-acting cylinder	CP96SDB80-700C	Stroke: 700 mm, bore: 80 mm

Qty.	Label	Component	Code / manufacturer	Main specification
2	X	Wire transducer	SIKO SGH10	Cylinder displacement measurement

4.2 Mechanical installation of components

The pneumatic components were connected using adapters and one-touch fittings compatible with 10 mm and 12 mm pneumatic tubes. These tube diameters were selected to remain close to the previous setup and to match the available fittings.

Airtightness was ensured using Usit rings when the interface between components was flat, and PTFE sealing tape for threaded connections. Components with suitable mounting holes were attached directly to the aluminium profiles using M8 bolts, washers and square spring nuts. For components without suitable mounting interfaces, custom supports were manufactured from aluminium-sheet offcuts using the pillar drilling machine and the folding machine.

The cylinder position sensors were mounted according to the SMC documentation. During preliminary actuation tests, the sensor positions had to be adjusted slightly toward the centre of the cylinder because the piston magnet was not reliably detected at the theoretical mounting positions. This reduced the effective stroke marginally but improved the reliability of end-position detection.

Figure 4: Recommended auto-switch mounting positions for end-of-stroke detection.

4.3 Pneumatic connections

The pneumatic circuit was assembled with the objective of minimizing tube length while keeping the layout accessible for inspection and future modification. The main connection lengths are listed in Table 4. Connections not listed were either directly coupled or shorter than approximately 5 cm.

Table 4: Lengths of the main pneumatic connections.

Components	Length [cm]	Tube [mm]	Components	Length [cm]	Tube [mm]
2_A-4	60	12	P_6-90_8	60	10
P_1-1_B	60	12	6_2-90_5	90	10
1_C-Q_1	10	10	6_2-90_6	30	10
90_2-T_1	20	12	6_1-3w_2	10	10
P_2-90_3	135	12	$3w_2-3w_4$	70	10
90_4-T_2	80	10	$3w_3-6_2$	20	10
T_2-2_D	10	10	$6_1-1_{D,2}$	20	10
$3w_1-1_{D,1}$	15	10	$1_{D,2}-P_4$	20	10
$1_{D,1}-6_1$	20	10	$P_5-1_{D,3}$	10	10
$3w_1-6_2$	70	10	$1_{D,3}-6_1$	50	10
2_E-Q_3	10	10	–	–	–

4.4 First pressurization and leakage inspection

After mechanical and pneumatic assembly, compressed air was introduced into the system through the first shut-off valve. The purpose of this first pressurization was to check the circuit for leaks, not to perform a complete dynamic test of the actuators.

Several leaks were initially observed, mainly at interfaces where Usit rings had been used. These connections were corrected by replacing some rings with PTFE sealing tape on threaded interfaces and by tightening the fittings. After these corrections, no significant leakage was detected during the inspection.

An oscillating hissing noise was also observed. Further inspection indicated that the noise originated from the SMC AK2000 check valve. Small pressure oscillations in the supply line caused the spring mechanism of the check valve to vibrate. After discussion, the check valve was removed from the system.

Figure 5: Schematic of the modified PESU system, inspired by the previous PESU circuit.

5 Automation and measurement architecture

5.1 Cylinder coordination

The two double-acting cylinders were intended to move continuously in order to reproduce a representative cyclic pneumatic load. The D-A93 and D-M9PW sensors provide end-position signals when the piston reaches the corresponding stroke limits. These signals were connected to an electrical control board previously assembled by Antti Sinkkonen. The board drives the directional valves and allows the cylinders to alternate according to the desired sequence.

The relay box was assembled using a FESTO 24 V DC ER mounting frame together with FESTO 162241 and 162242 components. Figure 6 presents the available schematic representation of this relay-based control system.

Figure 6: Schematic of the FESTO relay system used for cylinder coordination.

5.2 Data acquisition system

The measurement system was based on a Measurement Computing USB-2408 data acquisition device. The device was used in single-ended mode during preliminary tests. The possibility of using an additional USB-1608 or an MCC USB-2416-4AO device was considered in case differential-ended measurements became necessary. However, the USB-2408 remained the device in use, since a second device was not required as long as the single-ended configuration provided sufficiently stable signals.

Pressure sensors, flow meters and temperature sensors were assigned to analog input channels of the USB-2408 according to Figure 7. Since the USB-2408 measures voltage inputs, the current-output flow meter Q_1 required signal conditioning before acquisition.

Figure 7: Schematic of the sensor cable connections to the Measurement Computing USB-2408 data acquisition device.

The wiring diagram documents the allocation of the signals that were connected or prepared for acquisition. Pressure sensors P_1 to P_6 were assigned to channels CH0 to CH5. Flow meters Q_2 and Q_3 were assigned to channels CH7 and CH8, respectively, whereas temperature sensors T_1 to T_3 were assigned to channels CH9 to CH11. Channel CH6 remained available for the connection of flow meter Q_1 through the Nokeval 641 current-to-voltage converter.

The measurement architecture is summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Measurement architecture and scaling equations.

Signal	Sensor	Quantity	Output	DAQ channel	Scaling equation
P_1 – P_6	PSE530-M5	Gauge pressure	1 V to 5 V	CH0–CH5	$p = (V - 1)/4$ MPa
Q_1	PF2MC7501-F04-D-M	Flow rate	4 mA to 20 mA, converted to voltage	CH6	Expected equation after Nokeval conversion: $q_1 = 49.5V + 5$ L/min; to be validated experimentally
Q_2	PFMC7102-F04-E	Flow rate	1 V to 5 V	CH7	$q_2 = 247.5V - 237.5$ L/min
Q_3	PFMC7501-F04-E	Flow rate	1 V to 5 V	CH8	$q_3 = 123.75V - 118.75$ L/min
T_1 – T_3	Parker IQAN-ST	Temperature	0.25 V to 4.75 V	CH9–CH11	$T = \frac{400}{9}V - \frac{550}{9}$ °C

Two power supplies were required. A 5 V supply was used for the temperature sensors, whereas a 24 V supply was used for the pressure sensors and flow meters. The grounds of the two power supplies were connected together and linked to the analog ground of the Measurement Computing device in order to define a common measurement reference for the single-ended acquisition setup.

At the time of the latest laboratory checks, the pressure-sensor scaling had been

implemented in DAQami. The remaining analog channels still require final verification and, where necessary, implementation of their scaling equations before a complete measurement campaign is performed.

5.3 Temperature sensor scaling

The temperature sensors provide a voltage output between 0.25 V and 4.75 V, corresponding respectively to $-50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Assuming a linear relation between voltage and temperature,

$$T(V) = aV + b, \quad (1)$$

where T is expressed in $^\circ\text{C}$ and V in volts. The calibration points give

$$\begin{cases} -50 = 0.25a + b, \\ 150 = 4.75a + b. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Solving the system gives

$$\boxed{T(V) = \frac{400}{9}V - \frac{550}{9}}. \quad (3)$$

A preliminary measurement at ambient temperature gave approximately 1.84 V on the three sensors. The corresponding temperature is

$$T(1.84) = \frac{400}{9} \times 1.84 - \frac{550}{9} \approx 20.67\text{ }^\circ\text{C}, \quad (4)$$

which is consistent with room temperature.

5.4 Pressure sensor scaling

The PSE530-M5 pressure sensors provide a voltage output between 1 V and 5 V, corresponding to a gauge pressure range from 0 MPa to 1 MPa. Assuming a linear relation,

$$p(V) = aV + b. \quad (5)$$

The calibration points give

$$\begin{cases} 0 = a + b, \\ 1 = 5a + b. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Thus,

$$\boxed{p(V) = \frac{V - 1}{4}}, \quad (7)$$

where p is the gauge pressure in MPa and V is the sensor output in volts.

With the system unpressurized, the measured voltages were:

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 = 1.027\text{ V}, \quad V_2 = 1.052\text{ V}, \quad V_3 = 1.063\text{ V}, \\ V_4 = 1.012\text{ V}, \quad V_5 = 1.049\text{ V}, \quad V_6 = 1.016\text{ V}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The average voltage was 1.036 V, corresponding to

$$p(1.036) = \frac{1.036 - 1}{4} = 0.009\text{ MPa}. \quad (9)$$

This small offset is acceptable for preliminary validation and can be corrected during post-processing if required.

The PSE530-M5 measures gauge pressure. If absolute pressure is required, atmospheric pressure must be added:

$$p_{abs} = p_{gauge} + p_{atm}, \quad p_{atm} \approx 0.101\,325 \text{ MPa}. \quad (10)$$

5.5 Flow meter scaling

The flow meters provide analog outputs proportional to the measured flow rate. Flow meter Q_1 has a 4 mA to 20 mA current output and requires conversion to voltage through the Nokeval 641 signal converter. Flow meters Q_2 and Q_3 provide direct voltage outputs between 1 V and 5 V.

For Q_2 , the rated range is 10 L/min to 1000 L/min. Assuming linearity,

$$\begin{cases} 10 = a \cdot 1 + b, \\ 1000 = a \cdot 5 + b. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

This gives

$$\boxed{q_2(V) = 247.5 \cdot V - 237.5}, \quad (12)$$

where q_2 is expressed in L/min.

For Q_3 , the rated range is 5 L/min to 500 L/min. The corresponding linear relation is

$$\boxed{q_3(V) = 123.75 \cdot V - 118.75}. \quad (13)$$

Preliminary no-flow measurements gave 0.995 V for Q_2 and 0.973 V for Q_3 . The corresponding apparent flow rates are

$$q_2(0.995) = 247.5 \times 0.995 - 237.5 \approx 8.76 \text{ L/min}, \quad (14)$$

$$q_3(0.973) = 123.75 \times 0.973 - 118.75 \approx 1.66 \text{ L/min}. \quad (15)$$

These non-zero values under nominal no-flow conditions are most likely caused by sensor offset, measurement noise, calibration tolerance or small residual flow. For quantitative energy analysis, a zero-flow offset correction should be applied before integrating the flow-rate signals.

5.6 Nokeval 641 signal conversion for Q_1

Flow meter Q_1 provides a 4 mA to 20 mA output, whereas the USB-2408 requires a voltage input. The Nokeval 641 signal converter was therefore included in the measurement chain to convert the current signal into a voltage signal suitable for acquisition on channel CH6.

Following the main assembly phase, the converter was connected and its DIP-switch configuration was checked. The selected configuration was:

- 4 mA to 20 mA input;

- 0 V to 10 V output;
- 100 ms damping.

At the time of writing, the converter output had not yet been experimentally validated over the sensor range. Assuming that the selected conversion correctly maps the 5 L/min to 500 L/min range of Q_1 onto a 0 V to 10 V output, the expected calibration relation is:

$$q_1(V) = 49.5 \cdot V + 5, \quad (16)$$

where q_1 is expressed in L/min. This relation must be confirmed experimentally before it is used for quantitative energy calculations.

Figure 8: Input wiring for the Nokeval 641 signal converter.

Figure 9: Voltage-output wiring for the Nokeval 641 signal converter.

6 Final updates after the main assembly phase

After the main assembly period, additional checks and adjustments were performed in the laboratory. These updates concerned cylinder behaviour, sensor wiring, grounding, data acquisition and preparation of displacement measurements.

6.1 Cylinder friction and synchronization

During the first dynamic tests, the two cylinders did not move at the same speed. To isolate the cause, the pipes were removed from the cylinders, allowing them to move in a free-breathing configuration. The left cylinder required a higher force to move and descended more slowly than the right cylinder.

The measured fall times from top to bottom were:

$$t_{right} = 3.7 \text{ s}, \quad t_{left} = 6.1 \text{ s}. \quad (17)$$

The left cylinder therefore required approximately

$$\frac{6.1 - 3.7}{3.7} \times 100 \approx 65\% \quad (18)$$

more time than the right cylinder. The left cylinder was opened for inspection. No major visible defect was observed, the rod straightness appeared acceptable and the internal surface of the tube did not show clear damage. However, internal deformation or seal friction could not be fully excluded. Re-greasing and seal replacement were therefore selected as corrective actions.

6.2 Grounding and single-ended acquisition

Preliminary acquisition was performed in single-ended mode using the Measurement Computing USB-2408 device. The grounds of the two power supplies were connected to the analog ground of the acquisition device. This completed the common electrical reference required for stable voltage measurements from the powered sensors.

The single-ended configuration remains appropriate for the preliminary acquisition work provided that the signals remain sufficiently stable. If later measurements show excessive noise, drift or floating behaviour, differential analog inputs with a suitable alternative data acquisition device may be considered.

6.3 Displacement measurement

Pressure and flow-rate measurements are not sufficient to compute a complete mechanical energy balance. In order to estimate output work, actuator displacement must also be measured. For a double-acting cylinder, the mechanical work can be estimated from the force-displacement relation:

$$W_{out} = \int F(x) dx. \quad (19)$$

If the piston force is estimated from chamber pressure and piston area, synchronized pressure and displacement measurements are required.

Following the final laboratory discussions, SIKO wire transducers were selected for the position measurements of the two cylinders. One transducer was repaired for use on the first cylinder. The second sensor still required maintenance related to its wire before installation. Once both sensors are operational, their displacement signals may also be acquired using the USB data acquisition system. Their integration will make it possible to compare pneumatic energy input, recovered energy and mechanical output work over repeated cycles.

7 Remaining work and recommendations

The system was mechanically assembled and prepared for measurement, but complete experimental validation remains to be carried out. The following tasks are recommended before using the setup for quantitative efficiency studies:

- 1) experimentally validate the Q_1 measurement chain through the connected Nokeval 641 signal converter;
- 2) confirm the expected output scaling of the Nokeval converter under controlled flow conditions;
- 3) validate the remaining DAQami channels and implement their scaling equations where required;
- 4) measure and subtract zero-flow and zero-pressure offsets where necessary;
- 5) finalize the maintenance and installation of the second SIKO wire transducer;

- 6) connect and scale the displacement signals from both cylinders in the acquisition system;
- 7) define a repeatable test protocol with fixed supply pressure, cycle number, cylinder velocities and load-pressure conditions;
- 8) compare operation with and without PESU recovery under comparable operating conditions;
- 9) compare single-ended and differential acquisition only if signal noise becomes significant;
- 10) perform a complete energy-balance analysis over several cycles;
- 11) update the final wiring documentation once the displacement signals and Q_1 validation have been completed.

A future experimental campaign should measure pressure, flow rate, temperature and actuator displacement simultaneously. The compressed-air consumption supplied by the main source should then be compared between tests performed with PESU recovery and tests performed without PESU recovery while maintaining comparable cycle conditions. When the PESU is not in use, the required counterpressure can be created using the speed controllers so that the cylinder outlet flow is throttled while the inlet flow is not restricted.

8 Limitations

The main limitation of the project is that the final efficiency measurement of the PESU could not be completed within the available time. The project period was mainly dedicated to mechanical construction, pneumatic integration and preparation of the measurement architecture. Several delays were caused by missing components, cylinder-behaviour investigations, final signal-conditioning work and the limited availability of the exchange students near the end of the semester.

At the time of submission, the Nokeval 641 converter had been connected and configured, but its measurement output still required experimental validation. Similarly, SIKO wire transducers had been selected for displacement measurement, but the second sensor still required maintenance before the complete position-measurement setup could be commissioned.

As a result, the report should not be interpreted as a complete experimental performance assessment of the PESU. Instead, it documents the construction of a modular test bench and prepares the basis for future quantitative measurements.

9 Conclusion

The project resulted in a mobile and modular PESU test bench mounted on an aluminium-profile structure. The main pneumatic components were installed, the circuit was assembled

and inspected, the actuator control logic was documented through the FESTO relay-system schematic, and the sensor-to-acquisition wiring arrangement was identified for the Measurement Computing USB-2408 device.

Scaling equations were established for the temperature sensors, pressure sensors and voltage-output flow meters. The pressure-sensor scaling was implemented in DAQami during the laboratory follow-up. For the current-output flow meter Q_1 , the Nokeval 641 signal converter was connected and configured for a 4 mA to 20 mA input and a 0 V to 10 V output, but its final experimental validation remains necessary before quantitative use.

The need for actuator displacement measurement was also clarified. SIKO wire transducers were selected for this purpose, with one sensor already repaired and the second requiring additional maintenance before installation. Once these displacement measurements are integrated, the system will provide the signals required for a future comparison of compressed-air consumption and mechanical output work with and without PESU recovery.

From a technical perspective, the upgraded setup provides a cleaner and more flexible platform than the previous fixed-board arrangement. It allows future users to modify component positions, complete the remaining sensor connections and perform more systematic experimental studies.

The project also provided practical experience with pneumatic components, workshop manufacturing, sensor documentation, signal scaling and troubleshooting. It showed that a functional experimental system requires not only theoretical understanding, but also careful mechanical integration, reliable wiring, clear documentation and iterative testing.

Special thanks to Jyrki Kajaste and Antti Sinkkonen, who made the project possible.

Figure 10: Last version of the new PESU mounting frame.

10 References and documentation

- [1] Ceppari, L. Master's thesis on the original PESU setup. Aalto University. <https://webthesis.biblio.polito.it/27007/1/tesi.pdf>
- [2] Korpela, S. United States Patent No. US 9765786 B2, 2017. <https://patentimages.storage.googleapis.com/6a/2b/85/753248fbf83257/US9765786.pdf>
- [3] Finnish patent documentation: <https://patenttitietopalvelu.prh.fi/fi/patent/U20124166/>
- [4] PESU-related conference paper: <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/bdad0b42-d2e3-437b-a82c-a87f726dee0b/content>
- [5] SMC CP96 cylinder documentation: <https://www.smc Pneumatics.com/pdfs/CP96.pdf>
- [6] SMC PSE530 pressure sensor documentation: https://ca01.smcworld.com/catalog/Clean-en/mpv/cat02-23-ss-pse530_en/data/cat02-23-ss-pse530_en.pdf
- [7] SMC PFxx flow meter operation manual: <https://www.smcworld.com/assets/manual/en-jp/files/PFxx-OMS0002.pdf>
- [8] Parker IQAN-ST temperature sensor datasheet: https://www.parker.com/content/dam/Parker-com/Literature/Electronic-Controls-Division/Literature-files/IQAN-ST_uk_datasheet.pdf
- [9] Measurement Computing USB-2408 manual: <https://files.digilent.com/manuals/USB-2408.pdf>
- [10] Nokeval 641 signal converter manual: https://nokeval.com/app/uploads/2021/01/641_V4.0-4.1_2015-03-19_manual_EN-ID-3122.pdf
- [11] SIKO SGH10 wire transducer documentation: <https://www.siko-global.com/en/product-detail-page/sgh10>

A Appendix: component manuals

Shut-off valves 1_A and 1_B :

https://smccatalog.partbuilder.smc pneumatics.com/dl_catalogs/assets/manual/en-jp/files/VHx-OMQ0023.pdf

Shut-off valve 1_C :

<https://docs.rs-online.com/34c0/A700000009447995.pdf>

Air filter 2_A :

https://smccatalog.partbuilder.smc pneumatics.com/dl_catalogs/assets/manual/en-jp/files/AW-OMS0038.pdf

Air tank 4:

https://airtank.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/operation-manual-safety-information_EN286-2_revC_07092021.pdf

Directional valve 6:

https://smccatalog.partbuilder.smc pneumatics.com/dl_catalogs/assets/manual/en-jp/files/SY3000x-OMJ0003.pdf

Speed controller 7:

https://smccatalog.partbuilder.smc pneumatics.com/dl_catalogs/assets/manual/en-jp/files/ASx-OM00058.pdf

Silencers 8_A , 8_B , 8_C :

https://smccatalog.partbuilder.smc pneumatics.com/dl_catalogs/assets/manual/en-jp/files/AMX-OM-D023-D.pdf

USB-1608FS data acquisition device:

<https://files.digilent.com/manuals/USB-1608FS.pdf>

Aim-TTi PL303 power supply:

https://resources.aimtti.com/datasheets/AIM-PL+PL-P_series_DC_power_supplies_data_sheet-Iss5.pdf

GW Instek GPS-3030 power supply:

<https://www.gwinstek.com/en-global/products/downloadSeriesSpec/1272>

SIKO SGH10 wire transducer:

<https://www.siko-global.com/en/product-detail-page/sgh10>